

REVISED IN-DEPTH INTERVIEW PROTOCOL AFTER PILOT RUN

Interview Protocol Form

Institutions: _____

Interviewee (Title and Name): _____

IDENTITY AND NEWSROOM DIVERSITY

Authenticity

Describe all social identities you possess and carry around in your everyday life. For example, as a female, mother, people from a particular ethnicity, religious community, or social status.

1. How long have you worked in the journalism industry?
2. How long have you worked for your current company? How many different roles have you been in with your current company? Briefly describe your role as it relates to the company's operation.
3. What is your highest educational degree?
4. Are you single or married? Do you have children?
5. Where are you originally from/family life and your ethnicity?
6. What is the religion you grow with?
7. How do you describe your upbringing (*i.e., the treatment and instruction received by a child from its parents throughout its childhood*)?
8. How do you exercise and accentuate your possessed identities in the workplace and another social setting?
9. How do people perceive your identity?

Multidimensionality

Scholars suggested that multiple identities someone has will intersect each other and create distinct worldviews and experiences in every individual, hence although you and I are both women, we may have a different way of seeing things such as gender inequality because of other identities that shape us.

1. Are you noticing it happening in yourself, and could you give me an example of how those mixed identities play out in a particular area in your life?
2. Why did you choose to be a journalist, and how do you stay motivated at work?
3. How do your identities influence your understanding of your journalistic roles?
4. What kind of journalist are you, and what makes you unique from other journalists?
5. Does your gender or other identities hinder you in doing this job? How did you handle it?
6. What are the unique qualities you bring to the table as a leader?
7. How would you describe your leadership style, and how do your identities shape it?
8. What kind of leader do people expect you to be?
9. Do your gender and other identities hinder you in leading the organization? How do you overcome it?
10. What values are most important to you as a leader? Are there any leaders that inspire you?

11. Tell me about the hardest decision you've ever made as a leader. How did you decide which course of action was best?
12. How do you handle disagreements, respond to criticism, and solve a problem for your employees/employer?

Mobility

Some people find it difficult to exercise their identities in the workplace or other social settings. For example, the LGBT community could not boldly show their identity in society.

1. How free are you in exercising your identities in the workplace and another social setting?
2. Where, with whom, and in what condition do you find yourself able to fully immerse with your identity?
3. What factors hinder you from exercising your identity?
4. What strategy do you use to keep your identity salient?

Newsroom Diversity

As different identities shape people, cries for more diversity in companies are increasingly demanding.

1. How important is diversity in the newsroom, and why?
2. How do you treat and think of people with similar and different identities?
3. What do you think about the implementation of newsroom diversity in the journalism industry so far?

CHANGES PROCESS

Institutionalization

Scholars suggested that a diverse workplace is important for business success.

1. How do you think about it?
2. Could you identify any diversity problems in your organization and how it persists?
3. How would newsroom diversity change the news organization?
4. As a leader, are there any other problems you want to solve in your organization and how your identity may help you create changes?

Organizational learning

To reap a full benefit from a diverse workforce, companies should not implement diversity halfheartedly by only recruiting and retaining more people from underrepresented "identity groups" but also learning from their distinct experiences and knowledge.

1. What are your strategies to fully benefit from the knowledge and experiences of a diverse workforce?
2. How do your identities help you design learning strategies to solve the problem, and how positive are you in bringing changes?

3. Creating change is not easy as you may face resistance, so could you identify obstacles you encounter in making changes?
4. What changes have you accomplished during your time as a leader?
5. What changes can be brought into organizational structure, routine, and products for business success?

INNOVATION

Organizational structure

Innovation can produce changes to the way business is done and the products and services made by the companies. multicultural teams could be a source of intercultural competencies for the company, potentially generating innovation

1. What do you think about the role that innovation plays in business?
2. What are the structural challenges you encounter in bringing innovation to the organization?
3. How do you collaborate with others and accept new ideas?
4. How would newsroom diversity help the organization to innovate?
5. What kind of innovation can be brought to the way the organization is structured?

Routine

In the pursuit of learning, the organization should create a supportive routine to diversity, including rules, policies, and procedures.

1. How do your identities help you in creating a new and innovative routine that may encourage diversity?
2. How do you improve teamwork and business processes to increase creativity and innovative ideas?
3. What are the factors to ensure the successful implementation of innovation?

Products

Innovation is important for a media business to survive brutal competition in the digital age.

1. How do you define innovation in the journalism industry?
2. What kind of innovation does the journalism industry need today?
3. In your opinion, what's the greatest innovation in the journalism industry?
4. How do your identities or other news practitioners' identities contribute to creating innovation in the workplace or journalism industry?
5. What kind of innovation have you accomplished during your time as a leader?
6. Through your innovation, what problems do you want to solve?